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B142: Data Integration

Airbnb Market Investment Opportunity Analysis

Project URL:

The GitHub Link to the Project: <https://github.com/ENORIC/Data-Integration-Final-Project.git>

The YouTube Link Introducing the Project: <https://youtu.be/nB4wgDmf4nY>

Data source: The data for this project was obtained from a site called Kaggle.com. The link to the data set used in this project is:

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/computingvictor/zillow-market-analysis-and-real-estate-sales-data/data>

Introduction

The short-term rental market is a trend that has been of a big boom over the past decade. And one of the first few biggest companies that caught up to that trend and mastered it is AirBnB which is indeed most famous for their extravagant selection of short-term rental properties.

There is a pressing need for advanced analytical techniques that can ultimately precisely pinpoint lucrative opportunities as traditional real estate dynamics and the distinctive revenue potential of vacation rentals collide. In this report we will be discussing how we can resolve such issues by using Databricks along with pyspark sql, for conduction comprehensive analysis of Airbnb market performance compared to the local real estate properties using the sales data.

The following figure below is the ERD diagram, showcasing the tables and their relationship between the tables:-

(online.visual-paradigm.com, n.d.)

System design

The key components and the technology used, for this report we will be discussing how we can resolve those issue by using Databricks along with Apache pyspark sql on Databricks , for conduction comprehensive analysis of Airbnb market performance compared to the local real estate properties using the sales data.

The core component of the file system includes

- Creating a spark session which is crucial for the functionality of spark. This is used for efficiently handling a large amount a data based operations.

```
from pyspark.sql import SparkSession
```

- The main data frame (DBFS)is a could based storage system which is used to store all the CSV files that is needed for the project Airbnb and real estate data analysis.
- Databricks Notebooks: These notebooks the most sort out tool that is needed of creating the “data sciences and machine learning workflows”. It provides us a real time cell to code in multiple languages

Pipeline Structure:-

The data processing pipeline that this project follows is the ELT pipeline (Extract-Load-Transform. Over here the raw CSV files are first loaded into the Spark DBFS and then its transformed later on in the notebook using exploration codes. Which will be soon discussed.

Overview of the data sets: This project will be dealing with a total of 10 dataset .csv files. The key attributes of each files are:-

First, we have to do the **Extraction**:

The first batch of raw data is extracted from the DBFS which are:

- amenities.csv
- geolocation.csv
- market_analysis_2019.csv
- market_analysis.csv

```
amenities_df =
spark.read.csv("dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/amenities.csv", header=True, inferSchema=True, sep=";" )
geolocation_df =
spark.read.csv("dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/geolocation.csv", header=True, inferSchema=True, sep=";" )
market_analysis_2019_df =
spark.read.csv("dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/market_analysis_2019.csv", header=True, inferSchema=True, sep=";" )
market_analysis_df =
spark.read.csv("dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/market_analysis.csv", header=True, inferSchema=True, sep=";" )
```

```
amenities_df.printSchema()
geolocation_df.printSchema()
market_analysis_2019_df.printSchema()
market_analysis_df.printSchema()
```

amenities

root

```
|-- unified_id: string (nullable = true)
|-- month: date (nullable = true)
|-- hot_tub: integer (nullable = true)
|-- pool: integer (nullable = true)
```

geolocation

root

```
|-- unified_id: string (nullable = true)
|-- month: date (nullable = true)
|-- street_name: string (nullable = true)
|-- latitude: string (nullable = true)
|-- longitude: string (nullable = true)
```

```
market_analysis_2019
```

```
root
```

```
|-- unified_id: string (nullable = true)
|-- month: date (nullable = true)
|-- zipcode: integer (nullable = true)
|-- city: string (nullable = true)
|-- host_type: string (nullable = true)
|-- bedrooms: integer (nullable = true)
|-- bathrooms: double (nullable = true)
|-- guests: string (nullable = true)
|-- revenue: string (nullable = true)
|-- openness: integer (nullable = true)
|-- occupancy: string (nullable = true)
|-- nightly rate: string (nullable = true)
|-- lead time: string (nullable = true)
|-- length stay: string (nullable = true)
```

```
market_analysis
```

```
root
```

```
|-- unified_id: long (nullable = true)
|-- month: date (nullable = true)
|-- zipcode: integer (nullable = true)
|-- city: string (nullable = true)
|-- host_type: string (nullable = true)
|-- bedrooms: integer (nullable = true)
|-- bathrooms: double (nullable = true)
|-- guests: string (nullable = true)
|-- revenue: string (nullable = true)
|-- openness: integer (nullable = true)
|-- occupancy: string (nullable = true)
|-- nightly rate: string (nullable = true)
|-- lead time: string (nullable = true)
|-- length stay: string (nullable = true)
```

Then the same steps are done on the second batch of raw CSV files, these datasets that are shown above are the main data sets which are important to find the relationship between the sales properties data. There in total of 6 sales properties files. the first 4 sales properties files are combined for ease of manipulation and the last 2 sales properties

- sales_properties_total_zipcodes.csv

are combined as these are the sales properties that have “pools” more about it will be talked about in the report as well;

- sales_properties_total_zipcodes_with_pool_df

```
sales_properties_total_zipcodes_df = [  
("92252","dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sa  
les_properties_total_zipcode_92252.csv"),  
("92284","dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sa  
les_properties_total_zipcode_92284.csv"),  
("92314","dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sa  
les_properties_total_zipcode_92314.csv"),  
("92315","dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sa  
les_properties_total_zipcode_92315.csv")  
]
```

All sales property datasets with zip codes have been combined.

```
root
```

```
|-- Url: string (nullable = true)
|-- Zestimate: integer (nullable = true)
|-- Price: integer (nullable = true)
|-- Rent Zestimate: integer (nullable = true)
|-- Days On Zillow: string (nullable = true)
|-- Bathrooms: integer (nullable = true)
|-- Bedrooms: integer (nullable = true)
|-- Living Area: integer (nullable = true)
|-- Lot Size: string (nullable = true)
|-- Home Type: string (nullable = true)
|-- Street Address: string (nullable = true)
|-- City: string (nullable = true)
|-- Zip: integer (nullable = true)
|-- State: string (nullable = true)
|-- Country: string (nullable = true)
|-- Broker Name: string (nullable = true)
|-- Has 3D Model: string (nullable = true)
|-- Has Image: string (nullable = true)
|-- Has Video: string (nullable = true)
```

```
|-- isZillowOwned: string (nullable = true)
|-- sgapt: string (nullable = true)
|-- statusText: string (nullable = true)
|-- statusType: string (nullable = true)
|-- zip_code: string (nullable = false)
```

```
sales_properties_total_zipcodes_with_pool_df = [
```

```
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sales_properties_with_pool_zipcode_92252.csv",
```

```
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sales_properties_with_pool_zipcode_92284.csv"
```

```
]
```

The key attributes in these files are also the same.

Second, after once the extracted data **Loaded** directly into the spark DBFS that is in the cloud memory, the third step is to **Transform** the datasets and find useful insights.

Implementation

This section would should a detailed explanation of the codes in the two notebooks in the folder of Data Integration that are:

- Part 1:- Data Exploration
- Part 2:- Data Preprocessing

Part 1:- Data Exploration

Data explorations is done to get an overview of how the raw data from the dataset can be interpreted. It is vital for the project as it would helps us give a deep context and understanding of the dataset which can also help us to find the relationships between the multiple datasets. During data exploration on other factor that needs to be taken is the doing the quality check of the dataset, that is checking for any sort of null values or duplicates.

Once you load and read the entire data set we start that initial phase of data exploration.

First part of Daa Exploration is of course start by initialization of the spark session:

```
spark = SparkSession.builder \  
  .appName("Airbnb Investment Analysis – Data Exploration") \  
  .config("spark.sql.adaptive.enabled", "true") \  
  .config("spark.sql.adaptive.coalescePartitions.enabled", "true") \  
  .getOrCreate()
```

The AQE frame work is enabled as it is efficient for “planning and replanning of queries based on runtime stats”. Also calesePartitions is enabled so that the spark would read each CSV at a time. (Databricks.com, 2023).

Now we will be dealing with the important question that we will be dealing with these datasets and how data exploration can be done on them.

We start with data profiling

```
schema = StructType([
    StructField("Url", StringType(), True),
    StructField("Zestimate", IntegerType(), True),
    StructField("Price", IntegerType(), True),
    StructField("Rent Zestimate", IntegerType(), True),
    StructField("Days On Zillow", StringType(), True)
])

with_pool_df = spark.read.csv(path, sep=';', header=True, schema=schema)
```

This code will simply show spark that what kind of columns to expect even if it's a null values column, hence by specifying each column also by using “;” as the separator.

We move on to the most important step of data exploration and that is doing the quality check of the data. That is by checking if there is any “Missing Values” and “Count for any duplicate rows”

```
def assess_data_quality(df, df_name):
    print(f"\n {df_name} Data Quality")
    total_rows = df.count()
    print(f"Total Rows: {total_rows:,}")
    missing_counts = []
    for c in df.columns:
        missing_count = df.filter(col(c).isNull() | (col(c) == "")).count()
        missing_pct = (missing_count / total_rows) * 100
        missing_counts.append((c, missing_count, missing_pct))
    print("\nCheck for missing or null values")
    for c_name, m_count, m_pct in missing_counts:
        if m_count > 0:
            print(f" {c_name}: {m_count:,} ({m_pct:.2f}%)")
    duplicate_count = total_rows - df.distinct().count()
    print(f"Count for any sort of Duplicate Rows: {duplicate_count:,}")
    return missing_counts

assess_data_quality(amenities_df, "Amenities")
assess_data_quality(geolocation_df, "Geolocation")
assess_data_quality(market_analysis_2019_df, "Market Analysis 2019")
assess_data_quality(market_analysis_df, "Market Analysis Current")
```

Upon reading the files, a major anomaly was found between the files at that was one of the primary columns had inconsistent dataset. Hence came up with a solution to do Unified ID analysis, this analysis is crucial as it would help to ensure the data consistency through all the datasets. As some files have the prefix "AIR" under unified_ID and in the other files the id is clearly only numerical.

```
print("Amenities unified_id Format")
amenities_df.select("unified_id").distinct().show(10)

print("Geolocation unified_id Format")
geolocation_df.select("unified_id").distinct().show(10)

print("Market 2019 unified_id Format")
market_analysis_2019_df.select("unified_id").distinct().show(10)

print("Market Current unified_id Format")
market_analysis_df.select("unified_id").distinct().show(10)

print(" unified_id Pattern Analysis")

print("Amenities ID patterns:")
amenities_df.select(
    regexp_extract("unified_id", r"^[A-Z]+", 1).alias("prefix"),
    regexp_extract("unified_id", r"([0-9]+$)", 1).alias("numeric_part")
).groupBy("prefix").count().show()

print("Market 2019 ID patterns:")
market_analysis_2019_df.select(
    regexp_extract("unified_id", r"^[A-Z]+", 1).alias("prefix"),
    regexp_extract("unified_id", r"([0-9]+$)", 1).alias("numeric_part")
).groupBy("prefix").count().show()

print("Market Current ID patterns:")
market_analysis_df.select(
    when(col("unified_id").rlike("^([0-9]+$)", "numeric_only")
    .when(col("unified_id").rlike("^[A-Z]+([0-9]+$)", "prefix_numeric")
    .otherwise("other").alias("pattern")
).groupBy("pattern").count().show()
```

During the exploration one other major problem that was found was in the csv files was not all the data was separated by commas “,” instead it was separated by semicolons “;”. Along with fixing this the snippet also showed the overall Business analysis or the metrics for each attribute in the market analysis.

```
print("~~~ Revenue Analysis ~~~ ")
market_analysis_2019_df.select(
    mean("revenue").alias("avg_revenue"),
    min("revenue").alias("min_revenue"),
    max("revenue").alias("max_revenue"),
    stddev("revenue").alias("stddev_revenue")
).show()

print("~~~ Occupancy Analysis ~~~ ")
market_analysis_2019_df.select(
    mean("occupancy").alias("avg_occupancy"),
    min("occupancy").alias("min_occupancy"),
    max("occupancy").alias("max_occupancy"),
    stddev("occupancy").alias("stddev_occupancy")
).show()

print("~~~ Nightly Rate Analysis ~~~ ")
market_analysis_2019_df.select(
    mean("`nightly rate`").alias("avg_nightly_rate"),
    min("`nightly rate`").alias("min_nightly_rate"),
    max("`nightly rate`").alias("max_nightly_rate"),
    stddev("`nightly rate`").alias("stddev_nightly_rate")
).show()

print(" ~~~ Property Characteristics ~~~ ")
print("Bedrooms Distribution:")
market_analysis_2019_df.groupBy("bedrooms").count().orderBy("bedrooms").show()

print(" ~~~ Bathrooms Distribution: ~~~ ")
market_analysis_2019_df.groupBy("bathrooms").count().orderBy("bathrooms").show()

print(" ~~~ Host Type Distribution: ~~~ ")
market_analysis_2019_df.groupBy("host_type").count().show()

print(" ~~~ City Distribution: ~~~ ")
market_analysis_2019_df.groupBy("city").count().show()

print(" ~~~ Zipcode Distribution: ~~~ ")
market_analysis_2019_df.groupBy("zipcode").count().show()
```

Upon doing the data exploration an interesting question came up to the heat and that was to check how many properties possess a hot tub or a pool or maybe even both. Hence, the following code only focuses on amenities_df.

```

hot_tub_if_or_not = amenities_df.groupBy().agg(
  F.count(F.when(col("hot_tub") == 1, True)).alias("Property has hot tub"),
  F.count(F.when(col("hot_tub") == 0, True)).alias("Property does not have hot tub")
)
hot_tub_if_or_not.show()

print(" ~~~ Property has hot tub ~~~ ")
hot_tub_props = amenities_df.filter(col("hot_tub") == 1).select("unified_id")
hot_tub_props.show(20)

pool_distribution_if_or_not = amenities_df.groupBy().agg(
  F.count(F.when(col("pool") == 1, True)).alias("Property has Pool"),
  F.count(F.when(col("pool") == 0, True)).alias("Property does not have Pool")
)
pool_distribution_if_or_not.show()

print(" ~~~ Property has Pool ~~~ ")
pool_props = amenities_df.filter(col("pool") == 1).select("unified_id")
pool_props.show(20)

hot_tub_and_pool_distribution = amenities_df.groupBy().agg(
  F.count(F.when((col("hot_tub") == 1) & (col("pool") == 1), True)).alias("Property has both Hot Tub and Pool"),
  F.count(F.when(~((col("hot_tub") == 1) & (col("pool") == 1)), True)).alias("Property does not have both Hot Tub and Pool")
)
hot_tub_and_pool_distribution.show()

print(" ~~~ Properties with both Hot Tub and Pool ~~~ ")

hot_tub_and_pool_props = amenities_df.filter((col("hot_tub") == 1) & (col("pool") == 1)).select("unified_id")
hot_tub_and_pool_props.show(20)

```

Moving on the next question that was tackled in data exploration is the “sales of property” analysis. This code showed the overall:-

- Sale Properties by Zip codes
- Price analysis
- Home Type Distribution
- Status Distribution

```
--- Sales Properties by Zipcode ---
+-----+-----+
|zipcode|count|
+-----+-----+
| 92252| 73|
| 92284| 117|
| 92314| 57|
| 92315| 106|
+-----+-----+

--- Price Analysis ---
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|          avg_price|min_price|max_price|          stddev_price|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|844735.3456090651| 224999| 1800000|1087714.199163196|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
```

```
--- Home Type Distribution ---
+-----+-----+
|      Home Type|count|
+-----+-----+
|SINGLE_FAMILY| 353|
+-----+-----+

--- Status Distribution ---
+-----+-----+
|          statusText|count|
+-----+-----+
| House for sale| 323|
|New construction| 26|
|      Foreclosure| 3|
|          Auction| 1|
+-----+-----+
```

Please check the notebook for the code.

The last part of the data set was to check how many unique street names are there over all in the entire data set along with their latitude and longitude bounds. Upon running the snippet (please refer to the notebook) the output was.

```
--- Unique Street Names Count ---  
243  
  
--- Latitude and Longitude Bounds of the locations ---  
+-----+-----+-----+-----+  
|   min_lat|   max_lat|   min_long|   max_long|  
+-----+-----+-----+-----+  
|34.07944781|34.30483444|-116.9610963|-116.0022687|  
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
```

Part 2: Data preprocessing and Data Analysis I

Data preprocessing is one of the most core technical step in the spark pipelines. This is important as we do data cleaning, handling all the issues that was sorted out after the data exploration.

During data exploration we were able to find out that many columns that consists of numerical values, use "," a comma as a separation for instead of using a decimal point ".". So, to solve that:

```
def convert_comma_decimal_to_float(df, cols):
    """ Convert comma decimal strings to float for specific columns """
    for col_name in cols:
        if col_name in df.columns:
            df = df.withColumn(
                col_name,
                regexp_replace(col(col_name), ",", ".").cast("float")
            )
    return df
```

.cast() would cast the particular “column into type datatype” (Apache.org, 2024), so over here it replaces the “,” with “.” a full stop. The reason this happens is because the files that we are dealing with are CSV files, hence logically speaking as CSV files are Comma Separated Values all the values in the dataset are separated by “,”.

The next step of data preprocessing is Data standardization.

1. Taking out the prefix "AIR" for example "AIR10000347" and make it simply numerical based that is "10000347". Which will have standardized formants of the ID's all through the datasets. This would be easier for forming relationships between different datasets. Please do refer to the code snippet given in the notebook. Here is the output on how the new column would like:

The unified_id will be standardized through all the dataset that possess this column. As it is the primary key of many keys as well as the foreign key hence it is quite important for linking the datasets. This will change in Amenities, Geolocation, Market 2019 but stays the same in market analysis as it does not have any prefix.

```

Unified_ID standardization complete!

Unified_ID standardization verification:
Amenities – Before vs After:
+-----+-----+
| unified_id|Unified_id_standardized|
+-----+-----+
|AIR10052559|          10052559|
|AIR10211700|          10211700|
|AIR10344705|          10344705|
|AIR10424683|          10424683|
|AIR10471190|          10471190|
+-----+-----+

```

2. Now we will be combining and cleaning the market analysis data, this is done by adding the source identifier and combining the market data.

```

Combined market data: 146,547 records
Sample record preview:
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|Unified_id_standardized|  month|zipcode|          city|  revenue|data_source|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|          10000347|2019-01-01|  92315|Big Bear Lake|13948,75974|    2019|
|          10000347|2019-10-01|  92315|Big Bear Lake|449,9599915|    2019|
|          10000347|2019-11-01|  92315|Big Bear Lake|          0|    2019|
|          10000347|2019-12-01|  92315|Big Bear Lake|4949,679932|    2019|
|          10000347|2019-02-01|  92315|Big Bear Lake|          0|    2019|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
only showing top 5 rows

```

This is how the output looks so what the code did is,

```

market_analysis_combined =
market_analysis_2019_with_source.union(market_analysis_current_with_source
)

```

As you see the code uses union(), this operator is used to combine the result-set that is “return a new data frame containing the union of rows in this and another data frame”. In simple words “a new data frame containing the combined rows with corresponding columns “. (Apache.org, 2025).

3. This snippet is to handle any missing values and check the data quality.

```
Before cleaning: 146,547
After cleaning: 116,580 records remaining
+-----+
| revenue |
+-----+
|13948.76 |
|  449.96 |
|    0.0 |
| 4949.68 |
|    0.0 |
+-----+
only showing top 5 rows
```

This is the output that was received after running the main code (please do refer the notebook). What the code is first remove the negative values for revenue, rates and occupancy and also Handle occupancy > 1 (convert to decimal if needed) as well as removing records that have null values as well that is for the columns revenue, occupancy and nightly rate.

Deriving the business metrics:

The purpose of this code was to give the visual exploration of the TOP 10 listings with high occupancy; this was achievable by using feature engineering. This is done as the code derives a feature from the existing market_cleaned data frame.

Also later in the code also used a conditional logic of when().otherwise(). It means more like “if then else” (Naveen Nelamali, 2020).

```
.withColumn(
  "revenue_per_booked_night",
  when(col("annual_nights_booked") > 0,
    col("revenue") / col("annual_nights_booked")).otherwise(0)
```

what it does is that if annual_nights_booked is greater than 0 ">" it should calculate revenue/annual_nights_booked, and if its not greater or “else” the operator will assign the value 0. This would avoid the division by 0 which would be incorrect for this column particularly so it ensures the column always will have a valid value.

```

Derived metrics created!
Sample of derived metrics:
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|Unified_id_standardized|zipcode|bedrooms|revenue|revenue_per_bedroom|monthly_revenue|occupancy_pct|efficiency_score|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|10000347|92315|3.0|13948.76|4649.586588541667|1162.3966471354167|100.0|4649.586588541667|
|10000347|92315|3.0|449.96|149.98666381835938|37.496665954589844|3.2258063554763794|4649.586716937623|
|10000347|92315|3.0|4949.68|1649.8933919270833|412.4733479817708|35.48386991024017|4649.699697639085|
|10000347|92315|3.0|899.92|299.97332763671875|74.99333190917969|6.451612710952759|4649.586716937623|
|10000347|92315|3.0|11249.0|3749.6666666666665|937.4166666666666|83.33333134651184|4499.600107278827|
|10000347|92315|3.0|6749.4|2249.7999674479165|562.4499918619791|48.38709533214569|4649.586737960844|
|10000347|92315|3.0|899.92|299.97332763671875|74.99333190917969|6.451612710952759|4649.586716937623|
|10000347|92315|3.0|449.96|149.98666381835938|37.496665954589844|3.33333134651184|4499.600182747852|
|10035983|92315|3.0|9353.99|3117.9967447916665|779.4991861979166|100.0|3117.9967447916665|
|10035983|92315|3.0|8499.08|2833.0266927083335|708.2566731770834|100.0|2833.0266927083335|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
only showing top 10 rows

```

Processing and combing the sales data set:

ETL Pipeline for Real Estate Sales Data:

```

Total sales properties loaded: 383
Sample of raw combined sales data:
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|Price|Bedrooms|Bathrooms|Living Area|zipcode|has_pool|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|18000000|3|4|5470|92252|0|
|399990|3|2|1056|92252|0|
|575000|3|2|1577|92252|0|
|899000|3|2|1434|92252|0|
|369900|3|1|1040|92252|0|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
only showing top 5 rows

```

```

Sales data cleaned and improved.
Cleaned rows: 383
Cleaned and improved sales data here you go BOOM:
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|zipcode|has_pool|price_clean|price_per_bedroom|price_per_sqft|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
|92252|0|1.8E7|6000000.0|3290.676416819013|
|92252|0|399990.0|133330.0|378.77840909090907|
|92252|0|575000.0|191666.66666666666|364.61636017755234|
|92252|0|899000.0|299666.66666666667|626.9177126917713|
|92252|0|369900.0|123300.0|355.6730769230769|
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
only showing top 5 rows

```

This resulting output is because of code that was used to create the ETL Pipeline specifically for Real Estate Sales Data:

```
def load_and_clean_sales_data(files_list, has_pool=False):
    dfs = []
    for zipcode, file_path in files_list:
        try:
            df = spark.read.csv(file_path, header=True, inferSchema=True,
sep=";")
            df = df.withColumn("zipcode", lit(zipcode))
            df = df.withColumn("has_pool", lit(1 if has_pool else 0))
            dfs.append(df)
        except Exception as e:
            print(f"Could not load {file_path}: {e}")

    if dfs:
        return reduce(lambda df1, df2: df1.unionByName(df2), dfs)
    else:
        return None

sales_properties_total_zipcodes_df = [
    ("92252",
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sales_prope
rties_total_zipcode_92252.csv"),
    ("92284",
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sales_prope
rties_total_zipcode_92284.csv"),
    ("92314",
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sales_prope
rties_total_zipcode_92314.csv"),
    ("92315",
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sales_prope
rties_total_zipcode_92315.csv")
]

sales_properties_total_zipcodes_with_pool_df = [
    ("92252",
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sales_prope
rties_with_pool_zipcode_92252.csv"),
    ("92284",
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/sales_prope
rties_with_pool_zipcode_92284.csv")
]
```

```

sales_combined =
load_and_clean_sales_data(sales_properties_total_zipcodes_df,
has_pool=False)
sales_pool_combined =
load_and_clean_sales_data(sales_properties_total_zipcodes_with_pool_df,
has_pool=True)

```

This is the **Extraction** and the **Loading** part of the code where it defines `load_and_clean_sales_data`. What it does it read through each raw CSV files path which are categorized by the columns “zipcode” and “has pool”. After the operation finds the columns it immediately improves these two columns which is taken from the files “metadata” or the “raw file data”.

```

if sales_combined and sales_pool_combined:
    all_sales = sales_combined.unionByName(sales_pool_combined)
elif sales_combined:
    all_sales = sales_combined
elif sales_pool_combined:
    all_sales = sales_pool_combined
else:
    all_sales = None

```

This particular snippet does the Transformation as it combines the `sales_combined` dataframe with `sales_pool_combined` which are put into a single master or main file called `all_sales` dataframe.

```

f all_sales:
    total_rows = all_sales.count()
    print(f"Total sales properties loaded: {total_rows:,}")

    print("Sample of raw combined sales data:")
    all_sales.select("Price", "Bedrooms", "Bathrooms", "Living Area",
"zipcode", "has_pool").show(5)

    sales_clean = all_sales.filter(
        col("Price").isNotNull() & (col("Price") > 0)
    ).withColumn(
        "price_clean", col("Price").cast("double")
    ).withColumn(
        "price_per_bedroom", when(col("Bedrooms") > 0, col("price_clean")
/ col("Bedrooms")).otherwise(col("price_clean"))

```

```

    ).withColumn(
        "price_per_bathroom", when(col("Bathrooms") > 0,
col("price_clean") / col("Bathrooms")).otherwise(col("price_clean"))
    ).withColumn(
        "price_per_sqft", when((col("Living Area").isNotNull()) &
(col("Living Area") > 0),
                                col("price_clean") / col("Living
Area")).otherwise(None)
    )

    print("Sales data cleaned and improved.")
    print(f"Cleaned rows: {sales_clean.count()}")

    print("Cleaned and improved sales data here you go BOOM:")
    sales_clean.select("zipcode", "has_pool", "price_clean",
"price_per_bedroom", "price_per_sqft").show(5)

else:
    print("No sales data was loaded. Check file paths and contents.")

```

The fun part is the Feature engineering part where first the cleaning starts from “price” column to check if there are any null values.

Also, with the help of feature engineering, the code was also able to find out the “price_per_bedroom”, “price_per_bathroom”, price_per_sqft.

The next part in the notebook is to create a “main dataset” to save all the findings after the research which are quite essential for further analysis.

(P.S. → And that’s about it, it was actually fun to do this)

Just because of fun is feature engineering the next code is also a very fun feature engineering snippet. And it is called **Investment analysis features**. **(Please refer to the notebook for the entire notebook)** .

The new features that were engineered were:

- amenity_score: it’s simply a numerical score to showcase the properties that have a pool or a hot tub or maybe even both, it is engineered to show that if there is a pool or a hot tub to show 1, if there are both show 2 if there is none show 0. This could help us to find if amenities really do have a major interest in properties.

- `property_class`: it classifies properties in bases of their sizes like how much bedrooms space they have or if it's a studio or not. For example, Studio/BR, 2BR, 3BR, 4BR, etc. This can be used if having more bedroom space mean more profitability?
- `occupancy_tear`: Is simply directly corelated to occupancy rate which is showed in “%”
- `host_performance`: Used to only characterize what kind of host are there.
 professional → Professional
 Multi-Unit → 2-5 units
 Individual → For all other house types.

With the help of Investment Analysis features we can answer questions like ?
 hmm..

What combination of features (property class, amenities, host performance) leads to the best investment outcomes?

property_class	host_performance	amenity_score	avg_revenue	avg_occupancy	avg_profitability
4BR+	Individual	2	17828.926510641162	0.6481787303552545	12982.619788536553
3BR	Individual	2	10080.233400157853	0.6608597538844847	7789.493260148027
4BR+	Individual	1	10907.392578816662	0.5623181144477296	7350.488330176678
4BR+	Individual	0	8844.810994269068	0.5180387213899615	6057.105164714402
3BR	Individual	1	6618.7750642534065	0.5951465142623363	4714.293992616207
3BR	Individual	0	5087.36864699794	0.5328477461060274	3580.2944099727297

This is the output to that question well the goal for best investment outcomes is by checking the `avg_profitability` and that is simply calculated by $\text{revenue} * \text{occupancy}$. (Please refer to the notebook for further info about the code)

The next code deals with **descriptive statistical analyses for the investment features.** (Please do refer to the code in the notebook)

This code is purely made for the metrics and distribution for the investment features where we could visually read the information that is concise in tables.

Total records: 116,580
Unique properties: 6,859
Date range: 48 months

--- KEY METRICS SUMMARY ---

avg_revenue	avg_occupancy	avg nightly_rate	avg revenue_per_bedroom
6722.603499031498	0.5407332581855698	446.153408615642	1941.248950168326

--- PROPERTY DISTRIBUTION ---

property_class	count
3BR	79351
4BR+	37229

--- REVENUE TIER DISTRIBUTION ---

revenue_tier	count
Low (<15K)	106160
Low-Medium (15-30K)	8825
Medium (30-50K)	1326
High (50K+)	269

--- AMENITIES DISTRIBUTION ---

amenity_score	count
0	93290
1	20933
2	2357

```
--- HOST TYPE DISTRIBUTION ---
+-----+-----+
|host_performance| count|
+-----+-----+
|      Individual|116580|
+-----+-----+

--- GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION ---
+-----+-----+-----+
|zipcode|      city|count|
+-----+-----+-----+
|  92315|Big Bear Lake|66503|
|  92314|Big Bear City|25942|
|  92252|  Joshua Tree|13613|
|  92284| Yucca Valley|10522|
+-----+-----+-----+
```

visualization of the relationship between revenue tiers and average occupancy rates:

This graph shows key relationship between how much the property generates that is y revenue_tier and the average of how much is the space utilized that is occupancy_rate from 0 to 1 (0% to 100% for occupancy rates).

This graph also help to see the “demand” of the properties that is let’s say the graph show high occupancy and high revenue ties that means these properties are the safest investment can be considered a golden ticket (P.S. wish I had a golden ticket to life)

These finding are later then saved as a “parquet file” as a different path into the DBFS. Which would be later used during the analysis for answering few fun and interesting question in Part 3: Data Visualization and Data Analysis II.

```
ALL PARQUET FILES SAVED TO:  
dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/preprocessed_data/  
investment_features_master.parquet  
sales_properties_clean.parquet  
zipcode_summary.parquet  
host_performance_summary.parquet  
amenity_impact_analysis.parquet
```

Challenges and solutions

Few of the challenges that was faced during the Data exploration and the Data preprocessing were actually the silliest ones that made it so infuriating.

- Naming the objects or variables or calling the file path made it sometimes annoying, especially during feature engineering while creating new variables one of the solutions that I thought was to simply put matching names to the attributes in the raw CSV which made more sense to me
- During the first cleaning process that is in Data preprocessing, I almost lost around 90+ percentage of my current data because the numerical columns were using "," as a separations for number instead of using the decimal value "." I created a really aggressive cleaning process so to tackle the problem of loosing that much data I created a command within the code that solved me the problem of not loosing large amount of data.

```
numeric_cols = ['revenue', 'occupancy', 'nightly_rate', 'bedrooms',  
'bathrooms', 'guests', 'lead_time', 'length_stay']  
market_analysis_combined =  
convert_comma_decimal_to_float(market_analysis_combined, numeric_cols)  
market_cleaned = clean_numeric_columns(market_analysis_combined,  
numeric_cols)
```

Results

In the results we will be talking about the;

Part 3: Data Visualization and Data Analysis II. Specifically, Where we would be dealing with key question that can be tackled with the help of the newly create parquet file. But first we need to load the new parquet file.

```
BASE_PATH =
"dbfs:/FileStore/Airbnb_Market_Investment_Opportunity_Analysis/preprocess
d_data/"

print("Loading preprocessed datasets")
investment_df =
spark.read.parquet(f"{BASE_PATH}investment_features_master.parquet")
sales_df =
spark.read.parquet(f"{BASE_PATH}sales_properties_clean.parquet")
zipcode_summary =
spark.read.parquet(f"{BASE_PATH}zipcode_summary.parquet")
host_performance =
spark.read.parquet(f"{BASE_PATH}host_performance_summary.parquet")
amenity_impact =
spark.read.parquet(f"{BASE_PATH}amenity_impact_analysis.parquet")
```

1. Which zip codes have the best Airbnb revenue vs Real Estate price ratio?

The code deals with joins where:

```
sales_price =
sales_df.groupBy("Zip").agg(avg("price_per_bedroom").alias("avg_price_per_
bedroom"))

# Join with zipcode_summary on zipcode
joined = zipcode_summary.join(sales_price, zipcode_summary.zipcode ==
sales_price.Zip, "inner") \
    .select(zipcode_summary.zipcode, zipcode_summary.city,
            zipcode_summary.avg_revenue_per_bedroom,
            "avg_price_per_bedroom")
```

where the data integration is done for joining Airbnb performance with real estate sales data. That is done by joining the Airbnb revenue per bedroom which is available in the zipcode_summary also along with the average real estate sales per bedroom from sales_df. Hence, after making the join the zipcode_summary dataframe is then joined to the sales_price data frame. The key word “zip” are identical to both data frames and

that's how it is matched. The join is also an inner join so we will have *both* Airbnb performance data and real estate sales price data are included in the resulting joined data frame.

Which is then later run to visualize the code using `matplotlib` to answer the question.

Revenue-to-Price Ratio technically means lets say as per reading Zipcode 92252, the Revenue-to-Price Ratio is approximately 0.07 you might expect to generate \$0.07 (or 7 cents) in annual Airbnb revenue per bedroom for every \$1.00 you invest in real estate per bedroom.

2. How do the presence of a pool and/or a hot tub impact Airbnb property performance metrics — specifically occupancy rate, nightly rate, and estimated revenue — both individually and combined?

This code also deals with joins where to see if, does amenities have an impact on AirBnb performance ?

```
pdf2_pyspark = investment_df.groupby("pool", "hot_tub").agg(
    avg("occupancy").alias("avg_occupancy"),
    avg("nightly_rate").alias("avg_nightly_rate")
)
```

In the first step the code use the `investment_df` for leveraging the group properties, that is to check for the presence or the absence of the “pool” and

“hot tub” once it finds the relation for amenity combination the code will calculate the average occupancy and the average night rate.

And then the estimated revenue is derived when you;

'estimated_revenue'] = 'avg_occupancy' * 'avg_nightly_rate'

```
pool_stats = pdf2.groupby("pool").agg({
hot_tub_stats = pdf2.groupby("hot_tub").agg({
```

The value of both pool and hot tub are aggregated to see if there is “with” or “without”The rest of the code is show how to plot the derived data into visualizing it.

These graphs show the Average occupancy, Average nightly Rate and Estimated Revenue.

3. How does lead time (days before booking) affect nightly rates and occupancy?

This code snippet solves the question of If analysis of booking lead time impact on performance. (please refer the notebook for the entire code)

```
investment_clean = investment_df.withColumn(
    "lead_time_int",
    col("lead_time").cast("int")
).withColumn(
    "nightly_rate_float",
    col("nightly_rate").cast("float")
)
```

After the loading of the data from investment_df from the master or main data set there needs to be some cleaning done that is by giving data types to the column. For casting lead time in form of integer. Also filter out nulls.

```
investment_clean = investment_clean.filter(
    (col("lead_time_int").isNotNull()) & (col("lead_time_int") >= 0) &
    (col("lead_time_int") <= 365)
).filter(
    col("nightly_rate_float").isNotNull()
).filter(
    col("occupancy").isNotNull()
)
```

Then later in the code the lead_time_int is converted to days this is done by grouping for better understanding while reading the graph.

```

+-----+
|lead time|nightly rate|
+-----+
|      52| 449,979957|
|   NULL|      450|
|   NULL|      450|
|   NULL|      450|
|      8|      450|
+-----+
only showing top 5 rows

```


- Long Lead Time bookings (>90 days): Highest nightly rates approx. \$520, with highest occupancy, hence the best performing segment.
- Mid-Term Lead Times (31-90 days): Second highest nightly rates and good occupancy, indicating a stable demand that means it shows a strong performance.
- Short-term Lead Times (8-14 days): Nightly rates looks like it remains to be decent showing the lowest occupancy with around approx. 23%
- Last-Minute Bookings (0-7 days): Shows the lowest nightly rates lets say an approx of just above \$400 with low occupancy of around 20%
- 15-30 days: looks like good business, with moderate rates and occupancy it is just stable booking

4. Does the performance of the property get affected due to Seasonality Effects?

This code works on the idea of using average monthly occupancy and average monthly revenue, from where the performance pattern is depicted.

```
investment_with_month = investment_df.withColumn("month_num",  
month(col("month")))
```

this is the most important line if where, 'month' column is string like "2020-01-01", convert to date and extract month number which then creates a new column month_num. When done this way it would be much suitable for monthly aggregation.

```
monthly_summary = investment_with_month.groupBy("month_num").agg(  
    avg("occupancy").alias("avg_occupancy"),  
    avg("revenue").alias("avg_revenue")  
).orderBy("month_num")
```

And hence the aggregation takes place in this code snippet, where the investment_with_month df is grouped by the month_num column. The orderBy("month_num") also ensures that the resulting months_summary should be in the chronological order. For each unique month, the average occupancy rate and average revenue generated.

According to the graph

1. Peak season: December looks like the strongest months where the occupancy is the highest around 60% and the revenue also at the highest being at \$11,000. Hence, suggesting high demand along with premium rates well logical speaking due to the holidays or maybe the year-end travels.
2. January and July are also considered to be the strong months: showing a high occupancy in January also maybe an approx. of 62% and July an approx. of 60%. At the same time showing the revenue is moderate in July but as per the graph high in January, which logically indicates possible higher rates in January compared to July. July would be the best time for summer promotions.
3. May and September looks like an off-peak season: which shows the lowest occupancy and the lowest revenue, these months can be considered the weaker months as these months do not have any sort of major holidays that would boost the travel seasons.
4. Another interesting insight is that during months like March and April even though the occupancy droops the revenue tends to stay somewhat steady, this may also indicate that maybe the properties are charging a higher nightly prices but fewer books or maybe fewer booking but those booking must have been premium stays.
5. The last quarter of the year that is from October to December we can see a sudden peak in both occupancy and revenues. This could strongly suggest that its most probably due to the transition from fall to winter and as the holidays are coming up also due to the festive seasons like, thanksgiving, Christmas, new year.

Conclusion and Future work

This project was one of the coolest and project I have ever done well at least in a while. Even though it was infuriating, sometimes annoying and confusing it was of great joy to solve the puzzle of data integration and playing with the raw data to answer many interesting questions.

Well from the writer's point of views. One can say that project to be deemed successfully demonstrating the power of big data analytics using the great Apache Spark in Databricks. The main idea was to Airbnb short-term rental market and traditional real estate sales. This was able to be satisfied by building ETL and ELT pipelines which gave the necessary architecture to answer real-world problems and queries. From doing quality check on the raw CSV files to handling missing values to finally visualizing pondering questions.

Few of the key achievements where data cleaning and standardization of data moving further, working on feature engineering and creating new variables made us able to answer business-relevant question.

This project showed me how we can be provided a data-driven foundation for investment decisions, marketing and pricing strategies and optimization of property during different seasons. Which could help many real-estate or property owners.

Future work:

- Hopefully start with a much bigger dataset maybe a live dataset form AirBnb where more versatile and unique data can be transformed to our needs. With more selection of data more interesting question can be answered.
- The idea of bringing in a recommendation system maybe by using “cosine similarity”. Along with it maybe also do “Correlation analysis”.
- Machine learning for predictive Modelling.
- Time series forecasting, which would forecast revenue based on the particular season.
- Another fun interface would be having an automation and real-time data integration, that is by building an ELT or ETL pipeline for the pipeline process the data and shows real-time price feeds.

I could actually go on with the amount of future work that you can build onto this, as this is quite an interesting topic. At the end of the day I am thankful I was able to work on the project. Thank you Prof. Mazhar Hameed.

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